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Abstract

Physical and mechanical properties of the seed is an important factor in design and development of seed metering mechanism of any type of seed drill or planter, which helps to optimize the structural parameters for optimum performance. Determination and use of these properties are also essential for the design of a hopper for a planter for precise sowing of seeds. Physical and mechanical properties such as length, breadth, thickness, roundness, equivalent diameter, sphericity, bulk density, true density, angle of repose, and coefficient of friction were determined for the development of the seed metering unit. The mean values of length, width, thickness, geometric mean diameter, sphericity and roundness of two varieties blackgram (Pant urd-31 and SKM PD-3) were found to be 5.28, 3.86, 4.19 mm, 0.79, 0.76 and 5.45, 4.27, 3.65, 4.52 mm, 0.83 and 0.77 respectively. The average values of angle of repose for both varieties of blackgram seeds was found 25.01 and 24.91 degrees. The mean value of bulk density and true density of Pant urd-31 and SKM PD-3 blackgram varieties were obtained to be 830.4, 830.5 kg m⁻³ and 1457.1, and 1460 kg m⁻³ respectively. Lowest values of coefficient of static friction were observed in plastic (0.26 to 0.33) followed by those in case of galvanized iron (0.33 to 0.39), aluminum (0.36 to 0.38), mild steel (0.33 to 0.39) and plywood (0.38 to 0.48). These properties were used for the development of the seed metering mechanism.

Key words: seed, Black gram, hopper, metering mechanism.

Introduction

Blackgram [*Vigna mungo* (L.) Hepper] is a major pulse crop with a distinct role in Indian agriculture. This pulse is main ingredient of Indian diet, as it contains vegetable protein and supplement to cereal-based diet. It provides a major portion of the protein needs of the vegetarian population of the country. Blackgram is mainly cultivated in India, Pakistan, Sri-Lanka, Burma and some countries of South East Asia. The total production of pulses in the India during 2020-21 was 23.01 million metric tons (DAFW, 2023). Production of pulses in NEH Region during 2020-21 was 244002.63 tons. In Sikkim, share of blackgram in total pulse production was 52.95 % in 2018-19 (Sikkim, 2023). In Sikkim it is also known as 'Kalodal' or 'Panhelodal', and is widely cultivated in all the dry belts of South and West districts of Sikkim. In Sikkim, cropping area under Urd cultivation, production, and productivity were 3550 hectare, 2780 tones and is 783.10 kg ha⁻¹ respectively during 2018-19 (Sikkim, 2023). Common local varieties include Pant-U-19, Pant-U-31, T-9, Azad-urd-1, PDU-1, KU-300, Kalindi, SKM-PD-3 (Islam *et al.* 2013). In the North Eastern region of India, blackgram is grown under rainfed condition during all three crop seasons, namely Kharif (August-September), Rabi (September-November), and Zaid (February-March). During Kharif season, its sowing should not be delayed beyond 25th March during spring and sowing may be completed by 15th July. Design of a precise seed metering mechanism for sowing of blackgram seed that could increase the quality of feed index and decrease the missing index, multiple index and precision index for better planting, and the analysis of engineering properties of blackgram seed is essential for the design of the seed metering mechanism. The seed metering mechanism is essential to any planter's efficiency. It has an effect on the planter's design and performance parameters (Ajay *et al.* 2021). In the design of any planter, the physical properties of the seed are very important. Seed physical and mechanical properties not only influence planters and also different processing machines such as cleaners, graders, sorting machines, threshers, and transporting components in the processing of seed. Most physical properties which influence the design of seed metering and other components of seed planter are size, shape, mass, angle of repose, coefficient of friction, bulk density, and aerodynamic properties (Mohsenin, 1986).

Materials and Methods

The physical properties of seeds viz. size, shape, roundness, bulk density, angle of repose and thousand grain weight which affect the seed metering performance, were determined. Grain size of blackgram was determined for deciding groove depth of seed metering mechanism. Roundness of the seed was used for deciding

the radius of curvature of the groove. Bulk density and true density values were used in selecting the appropriate size of seed hopper. Angle of repose and coefficient of frictional property were determined to decide required slope for free flow of pulse seeds from the hopper. Coefficient of static friction values, as a measure of resistance, were determined for selecting hopper material for uniform and free flow of pulse seeds, the measurements were made for ten randomly selected samples, the average values of geometric mean diameter, sphericity, roundness, bulk density, true density, angle of repose, coefficient of static friction and thousand seed weight were considered for future design purpose. The methodologies adopted to determine the physical properties are discussed in the following sections:

Size and Shape of the seed

The geometric mean size and roundness of seeds affects the depth and radius of curvature of groove in seed metering plate. Two variety of black gram namely Panturd-31 and SKM PD-3 were collected. The size along three directional axes was measured as length, breadth, and thickness of the seed (Fig. 1). The size and shape of pulse seeds were the two important factors that helped in deciding shape and size of the seed metering plate. Three principal dimensions in the three mutually perpendicular directions viz. length (L), breadth (W) and thickness (T) was measured using digital vernier caliper make and model with least count of 0.01 mm (Fig. 2a). Further, geometric mean diameter (D_g), of the seeds was calculated using the equation 1 [Mohsenin (1986) and Gautam *et al.* (2016)].

$$D_g = (LWT)^{1/3} \quad \dots (1)$$

Where,

L = Length of the seed, mm

W = Width of the seed, mm

T = Thickness of the seed, mm

Shape affects the uniform free flow of pulse seeds from the metering plate groove surface. The criterion used to describe the shape of the seed is sphericity (ϕ). The sphericity (ϕ) was calculated by using the equation 2 suggested by Mohsenin (1986).

$$\phi = \frac{(LWT)^{1/3}}{L} \quad \dots (2)$$

The roundness (R_s) of the seeds was calculated using the equation 3 (Gautam *et al.* 2016).

$$R_s = \frac{[(W/L) + (T/L) + (T/W)]}{3} \dots (3)$$

Bulk density

Bulk density of blackgram seeds was determined by measuring the mass of seed of known volume. A 500 ml cylindrical container was filled thoroughly without any compaction and its weight was taken (Fig. 2b). The bulk density was calculated by using the equation 4 (Sahay and Singh, 2005).

$$\rho_b = \frac{M}{V} \dots (4)$$

Where,

ρ_b = Bulk density, g cm⁻³

M = Mass of seeds, g and

V = Volume of container, cm³

True density**SKM PD -3****Fig.1 Blackgram Varieties****Angle of repose**

The angle of repose (θ) was determined using an open-ended cylinder having 10 cm diameter and height of 20 cm. The cylinder was placed on a white paper sheet on a level surface and seeds were filled up to the top of the cylinder. The cylinder was then lifted slowly so that a conical heap was formed by seeds (Fig. 2d). With the help of vertical height gauge and measuring scale, cone height and base diameter of the cone were recorded. The angle of repose of blackgram seeds was calculated by the using equation 6. The experiment was repeated 10 times to determine mean angle of repose of blackgram seeds.

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{2h}{d} \right) \dots (6)$$

Where,

θ = Angle of repose, °

h = Height of the cone, cm

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The true density (ρ_t) is the ratio of the mass of the blackgram to its true volume. It was determined using the toluene displacement method (Fig. 2c). Toluene (C₇H₈) was used in place of water because it is absorbed by seeds to a lesser extent (Ravi and Venkatachalam, 2015). A know mass of seeds were immersed in toluene taken in a graduated cylinder and the volume displaced by seeds was recorded. True density was calculated by the using equation 5.

$$\rho_t = \frac{m}{v_t} \dots (5)$$

Where,

ρ_t = True density, g cm⁻³

M = Mass of sample, g

V_t = Volume of the toluene displaced by the sample, cm³

d = Radius of the cone, cm

Coefficient of static friction

The coefficient of static friction (μ) for blackgram was measured on five different materials viz., plastic sheet, plywood, aluminum, galvanized iron and mild steel by using a custom-made tilting platform apparatus (Fig. 2e). An open-ended wooden box (16 cm×8 cm×3 cm) was placed on the adjustable surface in horizontal position and then filled with the seeds sample. The box was slightly raised so as not to touch the surface. The adjustable surface was then slowly raised so that seed filled in a square box were in direct contact with the tilting table top. The table top was tilted slowly and the tilt angle was measured at which the seed box starts moving. The coefficient of static friction was calculated by the using equation 7 given by (Ghadge and Prasad, 2012).

$$\mu = \tan \alpha \dots (7)$$

Where,

μ = Coefficient of static friction

α = Angle of tilt, °

(a) Measurement of the dimensions of seeds

(b) Determination of bulk density

(c) Determination of true density

(d) Determination of angle of repose by toluene displaced method

(e) Determination of coefficient of static

(f) Measurement of thousand seed weight friction

Fig. 2 Measurement of seed properties

Thousand seed weight

One-thousand-unit mass of blackgram seeds was determined by measuring the weight of 1000 seeds with a digital electronic balance (CAH323, Contech, India) having an accuracy of 0.001 g (Fig. 2f).

Results and Discussion

Physical and mechanical properties

Physical and mechanical properties of two selected varieties of blackgram viz, Panturd-31 and SKM PD-3 were determined using methodology discussed in materials and methods and the relevant properties are summarized in Table 1, 2 and 3.

Size and shape of the blackgram seed

Table 1 Variations in dimensions of selected blackgram varieties

Seed Varieties	Values	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Geometric mean diameter (mm)	Sphericity	Round-ness
Panturd-31	Max.	6.04	4.16	3.63	4.45	0.87	0.81
	Min.	4.93	3.43	2.96	3.85	0.71	0.68

The values in terms of length, width, thickness, equivalent diameter, sphericity and roundness for two cultivars of blackgram were determined. The values of length, width, thickness and equivalent diameter for Panturd-31 variety of blackgram were 5.28 ± 0.37 , 3.86 ± 0.25 , 3.43 ± 0.20 and 4.19 ± 0.20 respectively. Similarly values of length, width, thickness and geometric mean diameter for SKM PD-3 variety of blackgram were 5.45 ± 0.32 , 4.27 ± 0.13 , 3.65 ± 0.14 and 4.52 ± 0.13 respectively. The values of sphericity and roundness for Panturd-31 variety of blackgram were 0.79 ± 0.04 and 0.74 ± 0.04 respectively. Similarly values of these parameters for SKM PD-3 variety of blackgram were 0.83 ± 0.03 and 0.77 ± 0.03 respectively.

SKM PD-3	Mean	5.28	3.86	3.43	4.19	0.79	0.74
	SD	0.37	0.25	0.20	0.20	0.04	0.04
	CV %	7.00	6.47	5.83	4.77	5.06	5.40
	Max.	5.96	4.44	3.87	4.75	0.88	0.82
	Min.	4.89	4.05	3.56	4.31	0.77	0.70
SKM PD-3	Mean	5.45	4.27	3.65	4.52	0.83	0.77
	SD	0.32	0.13	0.14	0.13	0.03	0.03
	CV %	5.88	3.04	3.83	2.87	3.16	3.89

Bulk density

Bulk density of seeds is an important parameter for deciding box capacity and for the seed rate of the crop. The bulk densities of both varieties were in the range of 820 to 840 kg m⁻³ as shown in Table 2.

True density

True density indicates the apparent volume of seeds by eliminating the voids in a cylinder. The true density of both varieties was in the range of 1445 to 1470 kg m⁻³ as shown in Table 2.

Angle of repose

Table 2 Bulk density, true density, angle of repose and 1000 seed weight of two varieties of blackgram seeds

Seed Varieties	Values	Bulk density (kg m ⁻³)	True density (kg m ⁻³)	Angle of repose (°)	1000 seed weight (g)
Panturd-31	Max.	837	1466	25.28	32.60
	Min.	820	1445	24.79	30.0
	Mean	830.4	1457.1	25.01	31.09
	SD	5.79	6.88	0.19	0.96
	CV %	0.69	0.47	0.75	3.08
SKM PD-3	Max.	840	1470	25.14	31.93
	Min.	821	1448	24.75	28.80
	Mean	830.5	1460	24.91	30.98
	SD	6.38	6.61	0.15	1.00
	CV %	0.76	0.45	0.60	3.22

This parameter is estimated to decide the grade of the seed hoppers sidewall to ensure free flow of the seed inside seed hopper. The angle of repose was obtained in the range of 24.75 to 25.28° for both varieties of blackgram seed selected for the study as shown in Table 2.

1000 seeds weight

1000 seed weight of the blackgram seeds is an important parameter to estimate the seed rate per hectare. The average values of both varieties ranged from 30.98 to 31.09 g as shown in Table 2.

Coefficient of static friction

In order to select suitable material for seed hopper, the value of coefficient of static friction for commonly available materials (galvanized iron, plywood, aluminum, mild steel and plastic) were estimated. Values of coefficient of friction as given in Table 3 for galvanized iron, plywood, aluminum, mild steel and plastic were

determined as 0.37±0.01, 0.43±0.01, 0.34±0.01, 0.36±0.01 and 0.30±0.01 of blackgram seeds for Panturd-31. Similarly values of galvanized iron, plywood, aluminum, mild steel and plastic for SKM PD-3 variety of blackgram were 0.35±0.01, 0.41±0.01, 0.31±0.01, 0.33±0.01 and 0.28±0.01 respectively.

Table 3 Coefficient of static friction of two varieties of blackgram seeds

Seed Varieties	Values	Galvanized iron	Plywood	Aluminum	Mild steel	Plastic
Panturd-31	Max.	0.39	0.48	0.36	0.39	0.33
	Min.	0.35	0.42	0.31	0.33	0.27
	Mean	0.37	0.43	0.34	0.36	0.30
	SD	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
	CV %	2.70	2.32	2.94	2.78	3.34
SKM PD-3	Max.	0.38	0.43	0.34	0.36	0.31
	Min.	0.33	0.38	0.28	0.31	0.26
	Mean	0.35	0.41	0.31	0.33	0.28
	SD	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
	CV %	2.85	2.43	3.22	3.03	3.57

Conclusions

The average values of length, width, thickness and equivalent diameter of Pant urd-31 and SKM PD-3 blackgram varieties were obtained to be 5.28, 3.86, 3.43, 4.19 mm and 5.45, 4.27, 3.65 and 4.52 mm, respectively.

The average values of sphericity and roundness of Pant urd-31 and SKM PD-3 blackgram varieties were obtained to be 0.79, 0.74 and 0.83, 0.77 respectively. Radius of curvature of the groove on metering plate were taken as roundness.

The angle of repose was observed in the range of 24.75 to 25.28 degrees for both varieties of blackgram seed. The lowest values of coefficient of static friction were observed in plastic (0.26 to 0.33) followed by those in case of galvanized iron (0.33 to 0.39), aluminum (0.28 to 0.36), mild steel (0.31 to 0.39) and plywood (0.38 to 0.48).

The average value of bulk density and true density of Pant urd-31 and SKM PD-3 blackgram varieties were obtained to be 830.4, 830.5 kg m⁻³ and 1457.1, 1460 kg m⁻³ respectively.

Physical and engineering properties of black gram seeds (i.e., seed size and shape, geometric mean diameter, roundness, bulk density, true density, angle of repose and coefficient of static friction) was determined to design the different parts of metering unit, such as groove size, metering plate thickness, capacity of hopper, seed rate of the crop, selection of the material for the hopper.

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